

BA'ZI XUSUSIY INTEGRAL TENGLAMALAR VA ULARNI YECHISH

Djurayev Yuldosh Xurramovich

Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti 2-kurs magistri

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7978017>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada ba'zi xususiy integral tenglamalar va ularni yechish, shuningdek aniq integralning ta'riflari hamda uning geometrik ma'nolari haqida so'z boradi. Maqola mavzusi misollar yordamida ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xususiy integral tenglamalar, tenglamalar va ularni yechish, integralning ta'riflari.

SOME PARTICULAR INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND THEIR SOLUTION

Abstract. This article talks about some particular integral equations and their solution, as well as the definition of definite integral and its geometric meanings. The topic of the article is explained with the help of examples.

Key words: special integral equations, equations and their solution, definition of integral.

НЕКОТОРЫЕ ЧАСТНЫЕ ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫЕ УРАВНЕНИЯ И ИХ

РЕШЕНИЕ

Аннотация. В этой статье говорится о некоторых частных интегральных уравнениях и их решении, а также об определении определенного интеграла и его геометрических смыслах. Тема статьи поясняется с помощью примеров.

Ключевые слова: специальные интегральные уравнения, уравнения и их решение, определение интеграла.

Aniq integral- matematik analizning asosiy tushunchalaridan biridir. Egri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan yuzalarni, egri chiziq yoylari uzunliklarini, hajmlarini, ishlarni, tezliklarni, yo'llarni, inersiya momentlarini hisoblash masalasi u bilan bog'liq.

$[a, b]$ kesmada $y=f(x)$ uzluksiz funksiya berilgan bo'lsin. Quyidagi amallarni bajaramiz.

1) $[a, b]$ kesmani $a = x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = b$ nuqtalar bilan n ta qismga ajratamiz va ular quyidagicha joylashgan bo'lsin.

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{n-1} < x_n = b$$

Bularni qisman intervallar deymiz.

2) Qisman intervallar uzunliklarini quyidagicha belgilaymiz:

$$\Delta x_1 = x_1 - x_0; \Delta x_2 = x_2 - x_1; \Delta x_3 = x_3 - x_2; \dots \Delta x_i = x_i - x_{i-1}; \dots \Delta x_n = x_n - x_{n-1};$$

3) Har bir qisman intervalning ichidan bittadan ixtiyoriy nuqta olamiz:

$$\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \dots, \xi_{n-1}, \xi_n$$

4) Olingan ξ nuqtalarda funksiyaning qiymatini topamiz:

$$f(\xi_1); f(\xi_2); f(\xi_3), \dots, f(\xi_{n-1}); f(\xi_n)$$

5) Har bir funksiyaning hisoblangan qiymatini tegishli qismaniy intervalning uzunligiga ko'paytiramiz:

$$f(\xi_1) \Delta x_1; f(\xi_2) \Delta x_2; f(\xi_3) \Delta x_3, \dots, f(\xi_n) \Delta x_n$$

6) Hosil bo'lgan ko'paytmalarni qo'shamiz va σ deb belgilaymiz.

$$\sigma = f(\xi_1) \Delta x_1 + f(\xi_2) \Delta x_2 + f(\xi_3) \Delta x_3 + \dots + f(\xi_{n-1}) \Delta x_{n-1} + f(\xi_n) \Delta x_n;$$

Shunday qilib, hosil bo'lgan σ yig'indi $f(x)$ funksiya uchun $[a, b]$ kesmada tuzilgan integral yig'indi deb ataladi va quyidagicha belgilanadi.

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^n f(\xi_i) \Delta x_i \quad (1)$$

Bu integral yig'indining geometrik ma'nosi, agar $f(x) \geq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda asoslari $\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_n$ va balandliklari $f(\xi_1), f(\xi_2), \dots, f(\xi_n)$ bo'lgan to'g'ri to'rtburchak yuzlarining yig'indisidan iborat.

Agarda bo'lishlar sonini, n ni orttira borsak ($n \rightarrow \infty$) da u holda eng katta intervalning uzunligi nolga intiladi, ya'ni $\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0$ bo'ladi.

Ta'rif: Agar S integral yig'indi $[a, b]$ kesmani qismaniy $[x_{i-1}, x_i]$ kesmalarga ajratish usuliga va ularning har biridan ξ_i nuqtasini tanlash usuliga bog'liq bo'lmaydigan chekli songa intilsa, u holda shu son $[a, b]$ kesmada $f(x)$ funksiyadan olingan aniq integral deyiladi va quyidagicha belgilanadi.

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx$$

$f(x)$ dan x bo'yicha a dan b gacha olingan aniq integral deb o'qiladi.

Bu yerda $f(x)$ integral ostidagi funksiya $[a, b]$ kesma-integrallash oralig'i; a son integralning quyi chegarasi, b son integralning yuqori chegarasi;

Shunday qilib, aniq integralning ta'rifidan quyidagini yozish mumkin.

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \lim_{\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n f(\xi_i) \Delta x_i$$

Aniq integral hamma vaqt mavjud bo'lavermas ekan. Aniq integralning mavjudlik teoremasini quyida keltiramiz. (Isbotsiz).

Teorema: Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz bo'lsa, u integrallanuvchidir, ya'ni bunday funksiyaning aniq integrali mavjuddir.

Shunday qilib, $\int_a^b f(x)dx$ aniq integralning qiymati $y=f(x)$ funksiyaning grafigi bilan va $x=a, x=b$ to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan egri chiziqli trapetsiyaning yuziga son jihatdan teng bo'ladi.

1- Izoh: Aniq integralning chegaralari almashtirilsa, integralning ishorasi o'zgaradi.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx = -\int_b^a f(x)dx$$

2-Izoh. Agar aniq integralning chegaralari teng bo'lsa, har qanday funksiya uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli;

$$\int_a^a f(x)dx = 0$$

haqiqatdan ham, geometrik nuqtai nazardan egri chiziqli trapetsiya asosining uzunligi nolga teng bo'lsa, uning yuzi ham nolga teng bo'ladi.

Aniq integralning asosiy xossalari

1- xossa: O'zgarmas ko'paytuvchini aniq integral belgisining tashqarisiga chiqarish mumkin.

$$\int_a^b Af(x)dx = A \int_a^b f(x)dx$$

Isbot: $\int_a^b Af(x)dx = \lim_{\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n Af(\xi_i)\Delta x_i = A \lim_{\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n f(\xi_i)\Delta x_i = A \int_a^b f(x)dx$

2-xossa: Bir necha funksiyalar algebraik yig'indisining aniq integrali qo'shiluvchilar aniq integrallarning algebraik yig'indisiga teng.

Masalan: $\int_a^b [f_1(x) + f_2(x)]dx = \int_a^b f_1(x)dx + \int_a^b f_2(x)dx$

3-xossa. Agar $[a, b]$ kesmada $f(x)$ va $\varphi(x)$ funksiyalar uchun $f(x) \geq \varphi(x)$ shart bajarilsa, u holda $\int_a^b f(x)dx \geq \int_a^b \varphi(x)dx$ bo'ladi.

4-xossa: Agar $[a, b]$ kesma bir necha qismga bo'linsa, u holda $[a, b]$ kesma bo'yicha aniq integral har bir qism bo'yicha olingan aniq integrallar yig'indisiga teng.

Masalan: $a < c < b$ bo'lsa, u holda

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx = \int_a^c f(x)dx + \int_c^b f(x)dx$$

5-xossa: Aniq integralning qiymati funksiyaning ko'rishiga va integrallash chegaralariga bog'liq, lekin integral ostidagi ifodaning harflariga bog'liq emas.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx = \int_a^c f(t)dt = \int_a^b f(z)dz$$

REFERENCES

1. M. Rahman. Integral Equations and Their Applications, WIT press, Southampton, Boston, (2007), 372 p.
2. A. M. Wazwaz. Linear and Nonlinear Integral Equations Methods and Applications, Higher Education Press, Beijing and Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, London, New York, (2011).
3. Rasulov T.H., Dilmurodov E.B. (2020). Eigenvalues and virtual levels of a family of 2x2 operator matrices. *Methods Func. Anal. Topology*, 1(25), 273-281.
4. Rasulov T.H., Dilmurodov E.B. (2020). Analysis of the spectrum of a 2x2 operator matrix. Discrete spectrum asymptotics. *Nanosystems: Phys., Chem., Math.*, 2(11), 138-144.
5. Rasulov T.H., Dilmurodov E.B. (2019). Threshold analysis for a family of 2x2 operator matrices. *Nanosystems: Phys., Chem., Math.*, 6(10), 616-622.
6. Расулов Т.Х., Дилмуродов Э.Б. (2020). Бесконечность числа собственных значений операторных (2x2)-матриц. Асимптотика дискретного спектра. *ТМФ*. 3(205), 368-390.
7. Muminov M.I., Rasulov T.H. (2015). Universality of the discrete spectrum asymptotics of the three-particle Schrödinger operator on a lattice. *Nanosystems: Phys. Chem. Math.*, 2(6), 280-293.
8. Umirkulova G.H., Rasulov T.H. (2020). Characteristic property of the Faddeev equation for three-particle model operator on a one-dimensional